

Literature Review: Transformational Leadership in Promoting Academic Research

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Abstract:

The objective of the paper is to review research on leadership style, leadership style shifting to the motivation of scientific research in universities. By summarizing the document, the article introduced the concept of leadership style, the concept of leadership transition, the characteristics of leadership transition and the influence of leadership transition. to the motivation of scientific research in universities.

Keywords: Leadership, transformational leadership, academic research

1. Introduction

Leadership style is a key factor to the success of every organization. Leadership style reflects the vision of the leader, influences the staff, and decides to build a strategy to achieve the vision of the organization (Paul & Doug, 2018). Appropriate leadership style will motivate employees to achieve their goals, and even make them work harder to overcome their limits to achieve greater results for the organization. In addition, leadership style will also help employees improve their satisfaction, engagement and loyalty to the organization (Fil, 2019).

Human resources are always considered as a valuable asset of business and society. Today, organizations need not only high-quality human resources, but also desire to promote individual performance of employees (David, 2018). Individual performance is an important factor creating a competitive advantage for the organization. And how to motivate employees to improve individual performance is always a challenge for leaders.

The role of leaders in higher education institutions is not an easy task, so leaders should create links around them. When leaders treat their followers as excellent individuals and attract their hopes and desires, a dynamic spiral effect will emerge and be maintained throughout until meet the defined goal (Yulk, 2013). Employees will contribute to the organization more, they will increase motivation, thereby increasing productivity. This can lead to an effort for the organization towards innovation with shared views and commitment to a common vision. Finally, individuals may be linked to complete the task "that they can reach a level of synergy in which the whole is greater than the sum of the parts" (Northouse, 2015).

This study will literature review the role of Transformational Leadership model in promoting academic research in institutions of higher education.

2. Leadership

There have been many attempts to identify leadership roles, which seem to be a complex phenomenon, and its definition depends on the person's perception and experience. Northouse (2015) states that the definition of global leadership is inconsistent because many different scholars have defined it in the context around them. Jon Gordon (2017) also described leadership as "a process in which leaders and followers interact dynamically in a particular situation or environment."

2.1. The concept of Leadership

For forty years, Burns (1978) noted, "Leadership is one of the least understood observations on earth." Although many later studies have identified leadership as a specific and observable phenomenon, however; There is no consensus on the accuracy of a successful leader in higher education (Donele, 2016). Leadership terms often refer to the social influence of competent actors and can be defined as those who accompany, rule, guide, or inspire others on their journey and drive them in the right direction (Taylor, Peplau and Sears, 2006).

Burns (1990) defines leadership as a process that is driven by motivated and valued individuals, many economic, political and other resources, in the context of competition and conflict. either independently or organized by both leaders and followers (Yulk, 2013).

Michael (2015) argue that motivation, inspiration, and personal development help to achieve the desired goal. Yukl (2013) argues that leaders are categorized according to their characteristics, including personality, personality, leadership behavior, interaction model, role relationships, perceptions, compliance influence, influence on followers, affect mission objectives, and influence organizational culture (Bass, 1990). The main differences in the definitions of leadership include differences in influencers, why influence is tried, and how it works (John, 2018).

Burns (1978) describes leadership as the process of developing an interactive relationship where leaders influence their followers and modify their behavior according to their opposition or reaction of follower. Yukl (2013) defines leadership as "the process of influencing others to understand and agree what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts. accomplish and achieve common goals. " The definition of Bass (1990) also describes leadership as the interaction between two or more members of a group involved in structuring or re-structuring a situation, and perceiving and expecting members. Bass (1990) defined leadership as a process that included influencing the goals and strategies of a group or organization, affects the members of an organization to implement strategies and achieve goals, affect group retention and identification, and influence the culture of the organization. W. Warner (2017) provides a framework of activities that leaders can self-assess. Leadership involves having followers and demanding a good balance between the leader and the follower. It is an organizational process involving the successful processing of complex tasks and changes (Yulk, 2015). Leadership can be defined as the process of interaction between leaders and subordinates with the goal of influencing subordinates' behavior to achieve a firm goal (John, 2018). Leadership is one of the most researched topics and has been evaluated at a number of different levels. Over the past millennium, different theorists have emerged (Burns, 2018).

The educational environment is constantly changing, making leaders increasingly important (Carl et al., 2018). Leadership is the initiator, the implementer, and the evaluator (Issa, 2014). According to Jean (2018), the key challenge for leaders is not just to deal with change but to change the capacity of their followers. An integral part of improving the organization's leadership is identifying individuals who are capable of becoming successful leaders at all levels (Monica, 2017). Leadership is not a solo act, it is an effort of the leadership team and followers. Leadership refers to the interaction between the leader and the subordinate in an effort to influence subordinate behavior to accomplish organizational goals (Yukl, 2015). Leaders must influence the followers to work together to achieve a vision. Successful leaders understand their own values and the value of their followers, to guide and direct the behavior. Shared values allow organizations to work together and act as an entity. A set of core values is often held to ensure that followers are working towards the same goal. Therefore, the cooperation between the two parties is the key to achieving and maintaining high efficiency (Northouse, 2015). Leaders must have an active role in creating a positive context for collaboration. A leader needs to assign tasks to every team member so that he contributes to a single task for the final result to succeed.

Leadership is an important factor because it affects employee attitudes and behaviors (Hugh et al., 2017). James (2017) describes leadership style as the way a leader interacts with others. Leaders must pay attention to the way their followers perceive their effectiveness (Peter, 2017). Burns (2018) introduced the paradigm of transitional leaders as opposed to transactional leaders in the context of education. He defined leadership as "stimulus watchers to achieve certain goals that represent the values and motivations held by leaders and followers." The ratings of the followers of their leader relate to the confidence they have in their leader. Changing the leader's beliefs is a key attribute of successful leadership, as it fosters respect, admiration, commitment, and confidence in followers. Consequently, recent attention must be given to the ongoing process of evaluating the followers of their leader (Burns, 2018). Successful leaders focus on the core values of their followers and ensure that everyone is working toward a common goal (Northouse, 2015). A leader must build a

shared value organization so that employees work together and act as one entity (John, 2018). Therefore, it is important to consider the impact of individual values, especially the value of leaders and followers, when determining the success of the leader.

In short, there are many different concepts of leadership. In the above definitions, the common point of leadership is the process of influencing, influencing, facilitating, and inspiring the followers to seek their voluntary participation in order to reach the goal, or mission of the group, and the organization. Dr Sackeena (2016) emphasized that the industry view of leadership cannot serve the purpose of education for the purposes and types of workers in other industries than educational institutions. Therefore, the study will examine leadership in education with an emphasis on higher education. And this is also the view of this study.

2.2. Definition of Transformational Leadership

The transformational leadership style James MacGregor Burns first conceptualized in 1978 (Burns, 1979). Burns defines transformational leadership that identifies possible possibilities in those who follow, satisfy their higher needs and attract followers. According to Bass (2008), transformational leaders motivate their followers to do more than the intended and think that they can be done. The characteristics of the transformational leadership style have undergone a process of development both in theory and quantification since it was first introduced by Bass (1985). In terms of origin, transformational leadership style comes from charismatic leadership; however, Bass argues that leadership's charisma is only one component of transformational leadership. Bass has produced four characteristics that constitute a transformational leadership style: leadership influence (idealized influence), employee interest (Individualized consideration), inspiration (inspirational motivation) and intellectual stimulation (intellectual stimulation) in it. The influence of leadership is also called the attraction of leaders (Bass, 1985).

There are many leadership theories and corresponding leadership style tools that have been supported by researchers in previous studies. However, much of leadership research since the late 1980s focused on the positive effects of transformational leadership (Avolio, 2018). In it, the most widely used tool to evaluate the transformational leadership style is the Multidisciplinary leadership questionnaire (MLQ) (Avolio & Bass, 2004). Research to identify effective leaders in organizations in various sectors such as business, education, government, health... has relied on MLQ to measure transformational leadership (Bass & Avolio, 1999; Berson et al., 2001). The first version of MLQ was developed more than 30 years ago (Bass, 1985), and this tool has undergone numerous corrections and adjustments. Different versions of MLQ have been used in more than 30 countries, and the translation of MLQ has been completed in many languages (Avolio & Bass, 2004). MLQ is formed based on comprehensive leadership theory (FRLT - full-range leadership theory) (Avolio & Bass, 1991). Avolio and Bass (1991) proposed FRLT based on previous work of pioneering scholars (Bass, 1985; Burns, 1978). This theory consists of three structures that represent distinct leadership styles: transformation, transactions, and laissez-faire. In addition, FRLT combines nine leadership elements including five transformation leadership elements, three transaction leadership elements and a laissez-faire leadership element (Avolio & Bass, 2004).

2.3. Characteristics of Transformational Leadership

By the MLQ (Bass & Avolio, 2004), the full-range leadership model determine including: Idealized Influence Attribution (IA), Idealized Influence Behavior (IB), Intellectual Stimulation (IS), Inspirational Motivation (IM), Individualized Consideration (IC). (Bass and Riggio, 2006).

- **Idealized influence (II):**

Idealized influence can further be divided into both attributes II(A) and behaviors II(B) for measurement, and thus this work refers to the five I's of transformational leadership rather than the four I's commonly referenced (Bass & Avolio, 2004).

The closest with idealized influence to prestige (Northouse, 2015) and that means the leader acts as a consistent role model. It is seen as a role model, admired and trusted (Bass & Riggio 2006). This has some similarities with the concept of inspiring a common vision, requiring passion and enthusiasm to draw and communicate future goals so that subordinates decide to commit to it (James, 2015). Ideal leaders will also listen to other people's dreams and help them recognize them (Northouse, 2015). Reputable leaders or influence are respected and respected by their followers. Leaders have a clear vision and sense of purpose and they are willing to take risks (Burns, 2018). Such leaders are generally valued for morality, trust, integrity, honesty and purpose. Leaders express the ideal influence when they improve organizational performance by engaging in risk with followers, maintaining consistency in their behavior, and credibility (Michael, 2015). This factor involves the moral growth of the leaders, as well as the way they become idealized in the minds and perceptions of the followers in the organization. Leaders must ensure that their behavior is ideal for the followers of the organization, giving them something to aspire, and thus affect their behavior and attitudes. Organizational benefits and organizational success (Micheal, 2015). In this way, followers feel the trust and positive atmosphere created by the leaders in the organization.

The ideal effect is described as trusting and supported by followers (Burns, 2018). Leaders must create the trust and support of the members of the organization by emphasizing the importance of goals, commitment to the goals of the organization and emphasis on holistic vision (Yulk, 2015). According to Klaus (2015), other aspects of ideal influence are also recognized by effective leadership models for all individuals in the organization, creating admiration, loyalty and confidence and the link between the individual towards the common goal.

- **Individualized Consideration (IC):**

As leaders shift attention to the individual's need for achievement and growth, this is called personal consideration (Bass & Riggio, 2006). According to Northouse (2015), a transitional leader looks at individuals through understanding individual motives and desires. From these needs, transformational leaders will have appropriate training programs for followers in the organization. In this way, transformational leaders help employees develop their strengths. In personal consideration, leaders accept and consider the different needs of subordinates. Leaders act as mentors or coaches, encourage two-way communication and practice positive listening (Burns). Individualized hands-on practice includes leaders who recognize good performance or provide constructive feedback when they find weakness. Some similarities can be seen when leaders help others to act, trust their subordinates and empower them, share leadership, and emphasize team effort (Jean, 2018). In fact, they are the ones who respect the decisions of subordinates, and can create an environment where people feel valued (Northouse, 2015).

Finally, leaders need to encourage, praise and value the individual and their contributions. This also includes general celebrations and ceremonies to build community awareness (Yulk, 2015).

- **Intellectual Stimulation (IS):**

Intellectual stimulation is the process by which a leader creates awareness of issues, encourages people to find new methods and techniques to solve problems and perform daily activities. (Hugh et al., 2017). The leader encourages creative and imaginative followers; change their way of thinking; as well as asking questions about their beliefs and solving problems themselves. Followers are encouraged to be creative and not be mocked or criticized for their mistakes. Ideas that differ from the opinion of the leader are not criticized but considered (Tim, 2018). Leadership also provides opportunities for employees to ask questions and this happens in conversations (Charles, 2015). The leader is "the first person to innovate," which means recognizing and

supporting good ideas, driving change, accepting risks and mistakes, and learning from them (Hugh et al., 2017).

According to Jon Gordon (2017), transformational leaders should understand the needs of followers to grow and develop within the organization. Therefore, leaders allow employees to engage in discussions and tasks that force them to think about creative solutions or apply oneself in creative ways. As a result, an understanding of the individual capabilities of the followers is essential for a transformational leader. This involves the second element of Transformational Leadership, in which the value of the leader's relationship with the followers is emphasized. Only through these relationships can leaders understand the personal skills and talents of their followers. So, with such understanding, leaders can assign better tasks to followers who will further enhance their skills and encourage growth and development.

Transformational leaders can also stimulate creative efforts of employees by rearranging issues and access situations in new ways. If a person makes a mistake, there is no humiliation (Avolio, 2018). Intellectual stimulation provided by a transformational leader forces workers to rethink ideas they may have not asked before. This allows the leaders to seek different perspectives when solving problems, from which to look at issues from different angles. Furthermore, through intellectual stimulation, leaders can also suggest ways to accomplish new tasks.

According to Burns (2018), intellectual stimulation can be "one on one" or at the organizational level. In such an environment, "leaders become so transformative and intellectually stimulated that they can distinguish, understand, conceptualize, and communicate with their associates opportunities and threats. the threat that their organization faces. " Under these conditions, innovative methods are explored to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization.

- **Inspirational Motivation (IM):**

Warner (2017) argues that motivational motivation means that the leader behaves enthusiastically and optimally. The individual and team spirit is motivated by the enthusiasm and optimism of the leader because good motivational inspirational leaders often speak optimistic about the future, expressing confidence that the item pepper will be achieved. It forms a unique combination of charismatic inspirational leaders (Northouse, 2015). Leaders share positive futures visions, display confidence, and communication expectations that subordinates want to meet due to the motivational actions their leaders show (Bass & Riggio 2006). Those motivating behaviors may be emotion or use of symbols, or anything that enhances teamwork (Northouse, 2015). It also requires that leaders establish values and beliefs, and bring in time, effort and action, exchange those values and help people to consider their own values (Fil J., 2019). Leaders motivate and inspire followers by providing meaning and challenge to their work. Followers accept goals, while leaders provide challenges and meanings and create teamwork (Charles B., 2015). Leaders focus on the ability of the leader to act as role models, communicate visions and use symbols to focus efforts (Yukl, 2015). The expectations that followers have to meet are clearly communicated (Avolio, 2018). In addition, these leaders encourage their followers to imagine conditions or future attractions attractive (Tim, 2018). In addition, these leaders communicate clearly and demonstrate commitment to the goals and visions of an organization. Such leaders tend to be able to articulate, in interesting and engaging ways, a vision of the future that followers can accept and strive for (Burns, 2018).

3. Transformational Leadership effects on motivating research on Higher Education

Leadership theory is a change within leadership theories convert most popular within psychology organizations. Transformational laeder stimulated and inspired to achieve extraordinary results and development by helping to meet individual needs as to empower them and adjusting the goals of the followers, leaders groups, and the larger organization (Allan, 2017). Burns (2018) define leadership change as "a leadership style focuses on the influence of revolutionary change within organizations through a commitment to the vision of the organization".

3.1. Transformational Leadership in Higher Education

Teaching and learning in the context of higher education, Carl et al. (2018) assessed the perceptions of academic research through the use of semi-structured interviews with faculty members. Burns (2018) distinguishes the conceptual framework of Transformational leadership, therefore, the findings from this study provide support for the application of the model Transformational leadership in the context of higher education. He also emphasized the role of Transformational leadership in an institution of higher education is "extremely important" and "nature decision" for institutions that university.

Mahesh (2015) argue that successful universities are likely to be the product of the kind of leadership that governs them. In addition, researchers say that successful schools often have employees who are inspired and motivated by their principals to commit to specific university goals. Once employees have committed to the vision of the school, they act as a community, working together to achieve and improve themselves, and they are fully aware that their actions are directly influenced to the success or failure of the organization.

The concept of leadership in higher education seems to be more complex, which includes the sense of need, aspirations and expectations of leaders in the desire to lead followers (Yulk, 2015). Tim (2018) concurred by identifying leadership as a "collaborative effort among team members." Nuraan & Yuself (2016) suggests that the role and function of today's leadership is integrated in higher education where academic leaders need to lead, motivate, or direct their organisation to adapt to the transformation of cooperation.

3.2. The role of Transformational Leadership on Employee Engagement and motivate Academic Research

Psychologist and leadership expert Kirk (2016) explains that leadership styles can have a positive impact on the organization. He also emphasized that the research evidence clearly shows that the group led by transformational leadership has a higher level of performance and satisfaction than other leaders because of the characteristics of transformational leadership style. Here are the features created by transformational leadership in inspiring and promoting research at the higher education level: Idealized influence attribution, idealized influence behavior, individualized consideration, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation.

According to Esther (2018), in order to increase inspiration and motivate followers in academic research, transformational leadership must ensure the following: honesty – Leaders deserve their trust. Transitional Concerns - Employees expect leaders to be oriented towards their future and for the future of the organization. Competence - Leaders need to demonstrate their competence in addressing situations to be competent to guide employees. They have a need to see their leader capable and effective. Inspirational - staff expect the leaders of enthusiasm, energetic and positive about the future. Encourage the heart: The leaders encourage the heart by rewarding others for their accomplishments. "The important task of a school leader is to help people get in and stay in optimal shape so they can do their best," Charles (2018) notes. Effective leaders pay attention to this need and are willing to praise workers for doing well. They use authentic celebrations and rituals to express appreciation and encouragement to others.

4. Academic Research – Improving the Individual Performance in research

Research at the university is primarily focused on creating new knowledge. This knowledge is often based on theory, and therefore, very impractical, so a useful product is not available. Longer time is needed for knowledge gained and theories are determined to have far-reaching and widespread impact on society. In addition, research done at the university may not respond to current problems or social issues.

4.1. The concept of Academic Research

According to Ary (2018), the scientific study of a type of text is a combination of knowledge and personal understanding of primary or secondary literature and research that is focused on focusing investigations and clarifying a specific issue. "A scientific study to meet the basic requirements must meet two criteria that define

a clear research goal and select the appropriate research method, and address all research questions addressed. "(Stephen, 2018). Fred & Maria (2018) also determined that the essence of an academic paper is guided by a thesis to prove or require a new conclusion on the chosen topic. The difference between academic research reports and other types of academic texts, in which academic research provides explanations from themed research from a variety of sources, rather than abstract ones. (Ary, 2018). In this paper, academic research is understood as research and development (R & D) is performed in the field of higher education, including universities, polytechnics, etc. and the research center that it is closely linked with higher education institutions. Two other proofs of this huge increase in academic research are among higher education researchers and the output of scientific papers.

Academic research is of fundamental importance to today's society. Social benefits from quality research and ethical research. However, there is increasing dependence and acceptance of the commercialization of research, ie research projects are increasingly determined on the basis of economic criteria. This behavior violates academic freedom and narrows the scope of research. As a result, researchers are not encouraged to engage in socially beneficial research and are required to accept research projects funded or dominated by the private sector to assess individual performance.

4.2. Type of Academic Research

There are two types of academic papers are often encountered in the study of the university: the theoretical and analytical studies. Theoretical research purpose is persuasion. Therefore, the writer should have clearly decided to show their stance on selected topics in the form of a thesis statement. Moreover, the thesis of a research paper reasoning usually comes from a controversial issue, so people can study and discuss potential counter author's research (Ary, 2018). In contrast to the paper analyzes what are often debated, authors of the study analyzed a definitive stance on the subject is selected and a question posed requires further investigation. This question is called the research question, it will not require users to write and maintain the stance of the target during the research process. The goal of the analysis is not convincing the audience that the author's idea is correct, instead, the goal is to give the author an explanation of the importance of primary and secondary sources in papers research, analysis and consolidation of the author of that topic (Fred & Maria, 2018).

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